

THE ACUTE AND CHRONIC EFFECTS OF HOT WATER IMMERSION ON INFLAMMATION AND METABOLISM

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Abstract The acute inflammatory response induced by exercise is suggested to improve the inflammatory profile and insulin sensitivity. As elevations in body temperature partly mediate the acute inflammatory response to exercise, passive heating may be a viable tool to improve metabolic health in individuals with a restricted ability to be physically active.

Purpose To investigate the acute and chronic effects of hot water immersion (HWI) on inflammatory and metabolic markers. **Methods** Ten able-bodied, overweight (BMI: 31.0±4.2 kg/m²) males were immersed in water set at 39°C for 1 h (IMM) and completed 1 h of seated rest at ambient temperature as a control condition (AMB). Venous blood was obtained prior to, immediately post and 2 h post-session for assessment of plasma concentrations of extracellular heat shock protein 72 (eHsp72), interleukin-6 (IL-6), nitrite, fasting glucose and insulin. Thereafter, participants underwent a 2-week intervention period (INT), consisting of 10 HWI sessions. Eight BMI-matched participants (BMI: 30.0±2.5 kg/m²) were included as control for the chronic arm of the study (CON). **Results** Plasma IL-6 and nitrite concentrations were significantly higher immediately after IMM compared with AMB ($p < 0.04$). Following the 2-week intervention period, the concentrations of fasting glucose ($p = 0.04$), insulin ($p = 0.04$) and eHsp72 ($p = 0.03$) were significantly lowered in INT compared with CON. **Conclusion** A single HWI session induces an acute inflammatory response and increases nitric oxide bioavailability, which could both positively impact on glucose metabolism. Indeed, the reduction in fasting glucose and insulin concentrations following the intervention period suggests that HWI could serve as a tool to improve glucose metabolism; with the reduction in resting eHsp72 concentration possibly contributing to this finding. Therefore, this study provides strong rationale to further investigate the health promoting potential of HWI in populations with disability.

Keywords Passive heating, chronic low-grade inflammation, Interleukin-6, Heat shock protein 72, glucose, insulin

Introduction

Chronic low-grade inflammation, characterised by elevated resting concentrations of pro-inflammatory proteins, is associated with a range of non-communicable diseases such as type 2 diabetes mellitus (Hotamisligil 2003). The acute inflammatory response following each exercise session is suggested to partly explain the reduction in chronic low-grade inflammation after chronic exercise training (Petersen and Pedersen 2005). However, inducing this response by exercise may not be feasible for people restricted from being physically active. As the increase in body temperature partly mediate the acute inflammatory response (Laing, Jackson et al. 2008), passive heating may be a viable tool to improve health in these individuals. This study investigates the acute as well as chronic effects of an applicable passive heating strategy (i.e. hot water immersion (HWI)) on inflammation and metabolism in sedentary, overweight males.

Methods

Ten sedentary (<2 h structured exercise/week), overweight males (BMI: 31.0 ± 4.2 kg/m²) aged 33.2 ± 10.1 participated in the intervention group (INT), while eight age, physical activity and BMI-matched males were recruited as control participants for the chronic arm of the study (CON).

Procedures

To assess the acute effects of hot water immersion, participants in INT were immersed in water set at 39°C for 1 h (IMM) and completed 1 h of seated rest at ambient temperature as a control condition (AMB). Venous blood was obtained prior to, immediately post and 2 h post-session. Thereafter, participants underwent a 2-week intervention period, consisting of 10 HWI sessions (5 sessions of 45 min, 5 sessions of 60 min, in water set at 39°C). CON visited the laboratory for two fasted, resting blood samples at the same time interval as the two resting blood samples taken for INT.

Core temperature during IMM and AMB was measured using a rectal probe. Concentrations of extracellular heat shock protein 72 (eHsp72), interleukin-6 (IL-6), nitrite, fasting glucose and insulin were assessed in plasma. In addition, flow cytometry was used to assess the expression of heat shock protein 72 in monocytes (iHsp72).

Statistical analyses

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Repeated measures ANOVAs were used to assess the acute effect of HWI on inflammatory markers (Condition x Time) as well as the chronic effects of the HWI intervention on resting markers of inflammation and metabolism (Group x Time).

Results

During IMM, core temperature increased from $37.1 \pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$ to $38.7 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$. The acute effect of HWI on inflammatory markers is shown in Fig. 1. In contrast to iHsp72 and eHsp72 ($p > 0.16$), the plasma IL-6 and nitrite concentrations were increased immediately following IMM compared with AMB ($p < 0.001$). Following the chronic intervention period, resting concentrations of glucose ($p = 0.04$), insulin ($p = 0.04$) as well as eHsp72 ($p = 0.03$) were reduced in INT compared with CON (Fig. 2).

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Figure 1. The acute changes in IL-6, eHsp72, iHsp72 and nitrite expression following AMB and IMM. Black lines represent individual data points, while bars represent the group mean. * Significant effect of Time, ^ significant Condition x Time interaction ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Fasting blood glucose and insulin concentrations following the chronic intervention period in INT and CON. Black lines represent individual data points, while bars represent the group mean. * Significant effect of Time, ^ significant Group x Time interaction ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion and discussion

A single HWI session induces an acute inflammatory response, indicated by acute elevations in IL-6 and an increase in nitric oxide synthesis, indicated by increased plasma nitrite concentrations. However, these responses were not accompanied by acute increases in iHsp72 or eHsp72. The 2-week HWI intervention period reduced fasting glucose and insulin, concomitant with lower resting eHsp72 concentrations, but independent of iHsp72 expression, plasma IL-6 and nitrite concentrations at rest, as the latter markers did not change following the chronic

intervention. Therefore, this study provides support for the use of HWI to improve aspects of the inflammatory profile and enhance glucose metabolism in sedentary, overweight males, and might have implications for improving metabolic health in populations restricted from being physically active.

References

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